

Supplemental Materials

Supplemental Figure 1: OD Data (no outliers marked or removed)

Supplemental figure 2: mScarlet-13 fluorescence without outliers marked or removed

Supplemental Table 1 : HiBiT assay selectivity as calculated by Ginkgo Bioworks

	Calibration curve in PBS		Calibration curve with lysis buffer spiked in		Calibration curve with preculture lysate	Calibration curve with production lysate	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pastoris</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pastoris</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pastoris</i>

R² of calibration curve	0.98	0.975	0.97	0.985	0.98	0.98	0.981
Residuals of calibration curve	unstructured	unstructured	unstructured	unstructured	unstructured	unstructured	unstructured
Measuring interval	0.012-1,59 nM	9.32 pM - 1691 nM	0.052-1,46 nM	7.88 pM - 2000 nM	0.121-1,48 nM	0.073-1,49 nM	8.66 pM - 2207 nM
Limit of Detection (LoD)	0.004 nM	3.08 pM	0.017 nM	2.60 pM	0.040 nM	0.024 nM	2.86 pM

Note: Measuring interval is defined between the from the limit of quantification (LoQ) to highest detectable luminescence signal; $LoQ = 10 * \sigma / S$, $LoD = 3.3 * \sigma / s$, where σ = standard deviation of the estimate of the y-intercept of the calibration curve and s = slope of the calibration curve.

Supplemental Figure 3: Standard curves and residual plots calculated by Ginkgo Bioworks. E coli data (3A); Pichia data (3B).

 20250122-Align-Ginkgo-Feasibility-Study-Ecoli-Final-Report.pdf slide 14, 26 - Ec

 20250122-Align-Ginkgo-Feasibility-Study-Pichia-Final-Report.pdf slide 14- Pp, slide 43

E. coli experiments:

RESULTS: STANDARD CURVES AND RESIDUAL PLOTS

DATA_VALUE vs. Standard Concentration (nM)

- Standard curves made with PBS and show strong linearity with high R-square values on both replicate plates
- The residual plots slightly expand as the concentrations go up, but generally unstructured.

Residual vs. Standard Concentration (nM)

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P. pastoris experiments:

EXPERIMENT 1 RESULTS: HIBIT ASSAY SELECTIVITY

Lysate sample matrix has no effect on the R^2 of the linear fit or residuals.

The HiBiT standard curve was prepared in a PBS buffer (according to the standard procedure), and null lysate (from the parent strain), lysis buffer, or PBS was spiked in to determine the effect on assay selectivity.

PRIMARY SCREEN RESULTS: HIBIT ASSAY STANDARD CURVES

All standard curves pass QC in the screen.

The standard curve R^2 in all plates is ≥ 0.99 and residuals are unstructured.

Supplemental Figure 4: Pp HiBiT colored by ONT copy number

